

SOCIAL SCIENCIES

QUALITY ASSURANCE IN SERVICES FOR PERSONS WITH INTELLECTUAL DISABILITIES: EVALUATING EQUASS APPLICATION IN DAY CENTRES

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Abstract

The article examines the application of the EQUASS quality standard and its impact on day centres providing services for individuals with intellectual disabilities. The study sought to determine how the implementation of EQUASS influences the activities of service users and what professional changes are observed by social workers. A qualitative analysis was conducted using semi-structured interviews with social workers, highlighting a client-centred approach that involves service users in decision-making, enhances professional well-being, and fosters leadership. The findings indicate that the standard has promoted improved communication through visual tools, strengthened the culture of teamwork, and led to a significant enhancement in service quality. It is emphasised that the EQUASS quality standard contributes to ensuring the social inclusion of persons with disabilities and increases their independence.

Keywords: intellectual disability, day centre, EQUASS standard, quality of social services, social worker, service user.

Introduction. The increasing expectations of social service users and society towards public sector organisations encourage these institutions to adapt, respond to new challenges, and strive for continuous improvement in the quality of their services (1). Adomaityte-Subacienė (2) state that this requires the development of robust management and assurance systems, as well as the establishment of standards. The growing scope of social services and the paradigm of new public management have firmly embedded the concept of quality within the field of social service provision. Ginaviciene et. al (3) argues that for service-providing institutions, it is essential to formulate quality objectives in order to ensure their implementation, basing decisions on evidence, continuous improvement, and a client-oriented approach that addresses the needs of service users. According to Adomaityte-Subacienė (2), the standardisation of services is one of the means of guaranteeing the effective delivery of high-quality social services.

In Lithuania, several quality standardisation systems are in operation: at the national level, the description of Social care standart (4) has been regarded as the quality standard for services; additionally, the international EQUASS quality assurance system is applied on a voluntary basis, alongside NOKAS, a quality standard developed by non-governmental organisations.

One of the objectives of the EQUASS quality system is to involve employees in the processes of quality improvement and continuous development, while ensuring that service users participate in the implementation of the quality system and receive high-quality services (5). In the development of social service quality systems, quality assessment indicators constitute a fundamental element, which is subject to ongoing debate

in the search for the most appropriate measures to reflect quality. Adomaityte-Subacienė (2) and Ciapaite (6) have examined the recommended principles and criteria for the provision of social services in pursuit of high-quality outcomes, both emphasising that the indicator of social service quality should not be understood as a final result, but rather as oriented towards the very process of service delivery. This study addresses the following research questions: (1) How does the implementation of the EQUASS quality standard transform the activities of social service users in day centres? (2) What professional changes are observed by social workers following the introduction of the EQUASS quality standard in these institutions?

Methodology. Research Methods:

The research employed two methods: analysis of scientific literature and a qualitative research approach. For qualitative data collection, semi-structured interviews were conducted using a prepared questionnaire.

Sample Characteristics: The study population consisted of social workers employed in day centres providing social services to individuals with intellectual disabilities, each with a minimum of three years of professional experience. A total of 11 respondents participated in the study. The average professional experience among participants was 13 years. All respondents were women. The research was conducted in accordance with ethical principles characteristic of qualitative studies. **Data Analysis Method:** The data were analysed using content analysis, which was considered the most appropriate method for the detailed examination and interpretation of the responses. The analysis followed the methodology proposed by Zydziunaite (7):

1. Reading the interview transcripts to identify the main aspects;

2. Segmenting the text and formulating individual statements;
3. Identifying significant elements;
4. Developing categories;
5. Forming subcategories.

In the study “Quality assurance in services for persons with intellectual disabilities: evaluating EQUASS application in day centres”, two principal themes were distinguished:

- **First theme:** service users’ rights and responsibilities, the benefits of collaboration with organisations, and the involvement of service users in service organisation.

- **Second theme:** promotion of personal leadership, enhancement of professional competence, and employee motivation.

The results were systematically analysed and compared with data from other scholarly sources to ensure the reliability of interpretation and theoretical grounding.

The **first theme** – “Expansion of Service Users’ Participation Opportunities under the EQUASS Standard” – was divided into three categories and nine subcategories. The results of the first theme are presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

Expansion of Service Users’ Participation Opportunities under the EQUASS Standard		
Category	Subcategory	Empirical Statement
Service users’ rights and responsibilities	Right to privacy	<p>“In order to safeguard personal privacy, the institution provides a designated space intended primarily for rest and relaxation; service users are aware that, whenever necessary, they may withdraw there to enjoy tranquillity.”</p> <p>“Without exception, all matters of hygiene are conducted in strict observance of privacy, while also taking into account the preferences of service users regarding particular private concerns.”</p> <p>“There are occasions when a service user wishes to spend time alone in peace. Regrettably, the institution does not possess a separate room for this purpose; nevertheless, respect for this individual right is ensured by making use of a more secluded area with fewer stimuli, which serves the need effectively.”</p>
	Right to self-expression	<p>“Within the institution, the right to self-expression is actively encouraged; in all activities individuals are supported in being themselves, with due regard to their personal abilities, and on more than one occasion they have surprised us.”</p> <p>“When discussing the rights of service users, it is important to emphasise that their capacities and desire for self-expression are particularly evident in creative activities.”</p>
	Visual tools	<p>“Following the introduction of EQUASS, a considerable number of illustrated materials were developed, including various posters; moreover, internal regulations were set out both in written form and through specific pictorial representations. All of this is undertaken to ensure comprehensibility for service users.”</p> <p>“With the implementation of EQUASS, a large interactive board was introduced, displaying an image for each activity, so that individuals who are unable to read may independently select their preferred activities. Experience demonstrates that service users themselves appreciate the significance of this board.”</p>
Collaboration with Organisations	Inclusion	<p>“Naturally, service users are pleased to be included in such initiatives”</p> <p>“It is important to involve them, to provide opportunities for participation; <...> often, owing to disabilities, they have few occasions to go out, and here it is so aptly referred to as ‘partnership’.”</p> <p>“Collaboration itself is highly inclusive of service users; they tend to be genuinely interested and motivated, and often require no encouragement at all.”</p>
	Voluntary participation	<p>“It is most gratifying that, having taken part once, the majority of service users remain satisfied and eagerly anticipate such activities again.”</p> <p>“At times, disagreements even arise among individuals over who will participate on a given occasion, as they enjoy it so much.”</p> <p>“Initially, some motivation was required; however, now that the partners are regular and consistent, service users have become accustomed to the activities and participate very willingly.”</p>
	Contribution of staff	<p>“We always make efforts to involve individuals as much as possible.”</p>

Involvement in Service organisation		<i>“It is of great importance that staff themselves strive to engage service users. It seems that prior to the introduction of EQUASS this was not emphasised to the same extent, whereas now we aim to ensure that everything is carried out with their involvement. <...> This, of course, requires considerable personal responsibility and patience on the part of staff.”</i>
	Submission of suggestions	<i>“With regard to the submission of suggestions by service users, even prior to the application of EQUASS our institution took their proposals into account, although now we place greater emphasis on encouraging them to submit such suggestions.” “Service users are familiar with the procedure by which they may submit suggestions; moreover, we encourage their representatives to become involved, to collaborate, and likewise, if they have proposals, they may freely present them.”</i>
	Freedom of choice	<i>“When selecting the activities in which a service user would most like to participate, complete freedom is granted. <...>. Although it often happens that an individual is talented and enjoys many activities, prior to drawing up the schedule we always allow them to choose.” “You know, the very awareness that one has the right to choose—even if in reality the difference between activities is not very great—serves as an encouragement; it enables them to feel important.”</i>
	Service User’s Opinion	<i>“Personally, I very much appreciate that nowadays individual wishes and opinions are always taken into account. Previously, most matters tended to be decided more by staff, whereas now we always approach the person, ask in which activity they would like to realise themselves, what they enjoy and what they do not. No longer is it the case that they must simply accept the staff’s decision.”</i>

The EQUASS standard emphasises the safeguarding of service users’ rights within institutions and encourages service providers to create appropriate conditions for the realisation of these rights. The data reveal that service users are aware of their responsibilities and adhere to them. Respondents identified the use of various visual aids as one of the benefits of EQUASS. Raudeliunaite et.al (8) argues that signs, illustrations, and other visual tools are easier to comprehend than text, which is particularly important given that, due to their disabilities, service users often cannot read or may even be non-verbal. Participation of persons with disabilities in social life is a key objective, achieved through diverse inclusion measures (9). Despite efforts to promote inclusion, stigma and prejudice against people with disabilities persist. To address this effectively, it is essential to organise partnerships that motivate and provide opportunities for service users to participate actively. Respondents highlighted that when attending activities in similar institutions, service users not only establish friendships but sometimes form long-term social bonds. Another positive aspect of EQUASS identified by the study participants is its strong orientation towards the service user. Staff are required to ensure that individuals are as actively involved in processes as possible. Social services must be delivered flexibly, taking into account the abilities, needs, and

preferences of service users (2). The EQUASS model stipulates that individuals should be included in the planning, provision, and evaluation of services. Accordingly, institutions must guarantee opportunities for service users to contribute suggestions. By involving service users in service organisation, employees themselves become more engaged, as such involvement gives greater meaning to their work. Raudeliunaite et. al (8) emphasise that the provision of high-quality social services requires attention not only to the final outcome but also to the process itself, ensuring that service users are included and their suggestions considered. A significant contribution to the improvement of individuals’ quality of life is the freedom granted to them to express their opinions Beneseviciute (10). Study participants also highlighted the importance of this freedom in achieving a more effective user-centred orientation. Geciene (1) argues that, according to the principles defining quality, the EQUASS model is particularly suitable for institutions providing rehabilitation, where considerable attention is devoted to meeting service users’ expectations and needs. The findings of this study confirm this assertion.

The **second theme** – “Changes in Social Workers’ Professional Practice under the EQUASS Standard” – is divided into three categories and six subcategories. The results of this theme are presented in Table 2.

Changes in Social Workers' Professional Practice under the EQUASS Standard

Category	Subcategory	Empirical Statement
Encouragement of Personal	Leadership – Interpersonal Relations	<p><i>“It is important that relationships among colleagues remain friendly and free from personal grievances, so as to avoid unnecessary disputes or disagreements.”</i></p> <p><i>“We must support and assist one another. I believe it is essential to show attention and care towards colleagues, demonstrating that they matter to us. In this way, we can effectively strive for the provision of high-quality services.”</i></p> <p><i>“Colleagues consistently encourage one another and provide strong support when personal development is being pursued.”</i></p>
	Encouragements	<p><i>“With the introduction of EQUASS, leadership has been increasingly promoted. This is evident among colleagues, and the encouragements are now more individualised. Moreover, recognition and encouragement from management have become more frequent, clearly reflecting a collective aspiration towards improvement.”</i></p> <p><i>“I have truly noticed a change. The administration is invested in us striving for something more. You see, it is implemented not through compulsion, but through the idea that it is not that we must strive for more, but rather that we choose to strive for more.”</i></p>
Strengthening Professional Competences	Freedom of Choice	<p><i>“I appreciate that nowadays there are no longer only general seminars for the entire institution; instead, we ourselves select the training sessions that are organised and of interest to us.”</i></p> <p><i>“Previously, the institution would order training and we would all attend. Even if the information was already familiar to us, it was not particularly useful, and we gained little from such sessions. Now we look at what appeals to us, since we ourselves understand which competences we lack, <...> experiences differ among everyone.”</i></p>
	Need for New Knowledge	<p><i>“In working with service users who have such diverse and individual needs, it often becomes necessary to refresh existing knowledge and to be able to apply it in specific situations. It is important to recognise where knowledge is lacking and to strive to improve it.”</i></p>
Employee Motivation	Achievement of Set Goals	<p><i>“For me personally, professional motivation is most enhanced by the service users' achievements, even if small, provided they are visible and tangible.”</i></p> <p><i>“Work motivation is greatly strengthened when the goals set together with the service user are successfully achieved, or even surpassed. <...> In such cases, professional activity acquires deeper meaning and motivates us to set higher objectives in relation to service users. <...> This is particularly evident now, with EQUASS, as we pay close attention to the client's opinion.”</i></p> <p><i>“In my view, no further incentives are needed; when one sees that a shared goal has been fulfilled, it is highly motivating—more so than any bonuses or gifts.”</i></p>
	Shared leisure time with colleagues	<p><i>“It is enjoyable to meet colleagues outside the work environment; we spend much time together at work, and such gatherings greatly strengthen our bond.”</i></p> <p><i>“Sometimes we meet for coffee after work, not to discuss work matters, but simply to get to know one another better.”</i></p> <p><i>“I am not sure whether this is linked to EQUASS, but recently we have begun such informal gatherings. <...> Perhaps this is related to the greater encouragement of leadership and the fostering of friendly relations among colleagues.”</i></p>

One of the fundamental principles of the EQUASS model is leadership. Minelgaite et al. (11) argue that leadership, as a factor, is highly significant for employee well-being and institutional performance outcomes. Its importance often lies not so much with the leader themselves, but with their followers – colleagues. The employees who participated in this study emphasised that interpersonal relationships among staff

play a crucial role in fostering leadership. In order to create a favourable workplace climate, positive relationships between employees are essential notes Juodisiute (12). The findings also highlight that, thanks to EQUASS, staff receive more encouragement from the administration. Professional well-being and personal development of social service providers are fur-

ther enhanced through training and competence-building. Abromaitiene (13) found that participation in supervision sessions enables employees to respond more calmly to emerging problems, strengthens collegial relationships, and reshapes perspectives on certain situations and their own roles within them. Naujanienė et al. (14) note that for social workers, supervision is important for professional improvement, enhancing relationships with colleagues, and reducing the risk of occupational burnout. Study participants also stressed the significance of the choice introduced through the EQUASS model. Staff training and seminars serve as tools for improving competences, developing personal qualities, and giving greater meaning to professional activity. Abromaitiene (13) further observed that continuous professional development contributes substantially to reducing stress and tension in the workplace. As previously noted, the field of social work is broad and dynamic; therefore, according to Gričiūtė et al. (15), it is vital for social workers to remain motivated and competent, enabling them to adapt to change, perform tasks more efficiently, and acquire new knowledge. An essential factor identified during the study as enhancing employee motivation is the achievement of set goals. In order to motivate social service providers, attention should be paid to enabling individuals to meet their own needs, while at the same time employing measures that contribute to the attainment of the organisation's collective objectives. More broadly, employees should be encouraged to develop their professional capacities as fully as possible, with favourable conditions provided for personal growth. Motivational measures are not static; they may change depending on circumstances or over time, as individual needs also evolve notes Nikolajenko (16).

It was further noted that shared leisure activities with colleagues help to reduce tension and improve interpersonal relationships. By spending time together, employees strengthen their mutual bonds and foster a stronger sense of teamwork. The analysis of research data revealed that time spent with colleagues is highly valued by staff. Bubnys et al. (17) support this view, emphasising that interpersonal relationships among employees are directly linked to job satisfaction. Such gatherings provide opportunities for staff to relax, detach from work-related problems, and gain a deeper understanding of one another.

Conclusions. The results of the study revealed that the implementation of the EQUASS quality standard in day centres providing services for persons with intellectual disabilities has led to significant changes related to service user involvement, the improvement of organisational processes, and the professional well-being of staff. Institutions have become more oriented towards the needs, opinions, and suggestions of service users. Decision-making, which previously tended to be carried out on behalf of the service user, has been transformed into a model of partnership, whereby decisions are made only after consultation with the service user. In order to achieve clearer communication and greater involvement, various visual tools have been introduced to present activity schedules, service users' rights, and general behavioural rules in an accessible manner. Such

changes strengthen the autonomy of persons with intellectual disabilities, increase their participation in service planning and organisation, and promote social inclusion.

At the organisational level, the implementation of EQUASS has encouraged more consistent planning, evaluation, and organisation of services, oriented towards concrete outcomes and their continuous improvement. Leadership promotion has been strengthened, greater attention is devoted to professional development, and new opportunities have emerged for competence-building tailored to individual staff needs. This enables the targeted strengthening of missing competences and the deepening of existing knowledge, thereby enhancing professional satisfaction and efficiency. The culture of teamwork has also been significantly reinforced, with staff more frequently initiating joint projects and engaging in collaborative decision-making. The findings further indicate that professional well-being is most strongly supported by collegial relationships and managerial encouragement for achieved results, although for some respondents the primary source of motivation remains the achievements of service users and the successful attainment of shared goals. The organisation of shared leisure activities with colleagues was identified as an important means of maintaining psychological well-being and reducing stress. Moreover, more active collaboration with social partners has increased institutional visibility within society and contributed to the strengthening of inclusion for persons with intellectual disabilities. The implementation of the EQUASS quality standard has fundamentally reinforced the orientation of institutions towards service users, stimulated the professionalisation of organisational processes, strengthened teamwork, and enhanced the professional well-being of staff. The standard has become an important instrument for the continuous improvement of service quality, the promotion of autonomy among persons with intellectual disabilities, and the assurance of their full social inclusion.

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